

Deliverable D2.3

Enabling data discovery at source using beacon-like mechanisms

Project Title (grant agreement No)	BeYond-COVID Grant Agreement 101046203		
Project Acronym (EC Call)	BY-COVID		
WP No & Title	WP2: Accessing heterogeneous data across domains and jurisdictions for enabling the downstream processing of COVID-19 and future pandemic episodes data		
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Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	Fundació Centre de Regulació Genòmica [CRG]		
Contractual delivery date	31/03/2024	Actual Delivery date	26/07/2024
Delayed	Yes		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	CRG		
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Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
17/05/2024		Aina Jené WP2 members	Shared first draft with WP2 members and contributed
21/05/2024		Jordi Rambla Aina Jené	Harmonised first draft for first review
27/05/2025		Aina Jené WP Leads	Shared D2.3 with WP2 leads for the first review
03/06/2024		Aina Jené	Harmonised second draft for final review
05/06/2024		Aina Jené Coordination	Shared D2.3 with coordination for final review
27/06/2024		Aina Jené	Deliverable submitted
08/07/2024		ELSI	Ethics review

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.3, titled "Enabling data discovery at source using beacon-like mechanisms," presents the outcomes and advancements achieved by Work Package 2 (WP2) partners within the BY-COVID project. The report delineates existing data discovery mechanisms and introduces novel cross-domain data discovery through extensions to the Beacon and the Beacon Network technologies, particularly focusing on its application to COVID-19 data.

Throughout the duration of the project, significant progress has been made in expanding standard data discovery mechanisms. Collaborative efforts have resulted in the enhancement of Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) Beacon-based mechanisms, enabling efficient data discovery at its source. This deliverable describes eight different Beacon implementations from BY-COVID partners, and other institutions in Europe and other parts of the world (Canada and Australia). These beacons share cross-domain data, from viral genomes and epidemiology to rich patient information or combined viral and host genomes from the same donors.

The achievements prove the commitment to enabling data discovery at its source. By extending Beacon technologies, the project has paved the way for enhanced data accessibility and interoperability across various research domains. Nevertheless, the deliverable shows that the use of popular models and dictionaries (like OMOP¹ or ISARIC eCRF²) is not enough to achieve solid interoperability, although it enormously reduces the harmonisation gap and opens the door to generation of tools to bridge these gaps. These advancements signify a crucial step forward in empowering researchers to efficiently access and use diverse datasets, ultimately contributing to more informed decision-making and research outcomes.

¹ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

² <https://isaric.net/ccp/>

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'.]

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures practice that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	Yes
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	No
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform	No
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	Yes
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	Yes
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.	No
	4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	No

<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.</p>	No
<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	Yes

	3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.	Yes
	4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.	No

3. Introduction

3.1 Types of discovery: Catalogue vs Data

Discovering research data for re-analysis or other purposes could be done at different levels of granularity. Typically, there is an initial discovery step over available catalogues by browsing Internet known sites. These catalogues usually contain a description of the study, the dataset, related publications and, depending on the provider, a list of variables included in the study and some figures that describe the distribution of values for each variable. An example of the latter could be an age pyramid or a pie chart showing sex proportions (*Figure 1*). This level of discovery granularity could be sufficient if the spotted datasets fulfil all of the searched requirements.

Figure 1: Age and sex variables description and distribution in the BCQ19 Beacon

Source: <https://bqc19.bento.sd4h.ca/#/en/>

However, if the researcher is looking for a specific combination of attributes like: “adults diagnosed with COVID-19 within the last year, who are fully vaccinated and have no underlying health conditions” the only options available to the researcher are: 1) to contact the authors and ask for that specific set of attributes, or 2) request access to the data and, if granted, check it by themselves. This applies to open access or controlled access data. These are viable options when the number of datasets to deal with is small, and when the controllers of the datasets are open to obtain the requested number on behalf of the requester.

Data discovery, in a broad sense, is the set of processes and tools that allows users to understand which data is available, where it is stored, and how to get some information or details about it. In particular, the interest goes in the set of processes and tools that provide a better understanding of the information included in a dataset, by allowing queries that return the number of records that fulfil a given set of conditions.

3.2 What is discovery and harmonisation at source?

Data harmonisation is a crucial process in both research projects and healthcare systems. It involves ensuring that data from various sources are standardised and compatible, despite potential differences in language, measurement units, or data standards.

For instance, consider a scenario where one dataset records height in *centimetres* while another uses *feet*. Without harmonisation, combining these datasets for analysis would be challenging, if not impossible. Harmonising data resolves such discrepancies, making it feasible to conduct meaningful analyses across diverse datasets.

Harmonising data is essential for several reasons. Firstly, it enhances the accuracy and reliability of analyses by ensuring that all data are consistent and comparable. This consistency reduces the likelihood of errors and misinterpretations that can arise from disparate data sources. Secondly, harmonised data facilitates interoperability, collaboration, and knowledge sharing across institutions and research projects. By adopting common standards and formats, researchers can easily exchange and integrate data, fostering collective insights and advancements in knowledge.

There are two primary approaches to data harmonisation: harmonisation at the source and harmonisation at the destination. Harmonisation at the source involves standardising data at the point of origin. This approach leverages the expertise and familiarity of those closest to the data, resulting in more accurate and contextually relevant harmonisation. On the other hand, harmonisation at the destination occurs when data are standardised during the analysis phase. While this approach offers flexibility and central control, it may lack the nuanced understanding of data intricacies present at the source.

In the context of the BY-COVID project, there has been an initial collaborative work on metadata harmonisation at domain level³, as well as creating a common metadata model for the inclusion of relevant datasets into the COVID-19 Data Portal⁴. To summarise, this common metadata model comprises four key sections:

1. Database Section of XML, which defines metadata fields related to databases or data providers
2. Each Entry Section of XML, which specifies metadata attributes for individual entries or datasets within a database
3. Each Entry Section of XML - Cross-references, covering cross-references of entries to other repositories and suggesting new metadata fields.
4. Each Entry Section of XML - Additional Fields, providing extra metadata attributes for entries or datasets

```
<database>
  <name>Database Name</name>
  <description>Database Description</description>
  <release>Release tag or number</release>
  <release_date>Release date</release_date>
  <entry_count>Number of entries</entry_count>
  <entries>
    <entry id="Dataset_ID_1">
      <name>Name of the Dataset</name>
      <description>Description of the dataset</description>
      <cross_references>
        <ref dbkey="CHEBI:16551" dbname="ChEBI">
          <ref dbkey="MTBLC16551" dbname="MetaboLights">
            <ref dbkey="CHEBI:16810" dbname="ChEBI">
          </cross_references>
        <additional_fields>
          <field name="repository">Repository</field>
          <field name="omics_type">Omics Type</field>
        </additional_fields>
      </entry>
    </entries>
  </database>
```

Figure 2: Example of an XML schema for the COVID-19 Data Portal common metadata model.

Thanks to this common metadata model, many data resources⁵ have added their entries into the COVID-19 Data Portal⁶ in a harmonised manner.

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/7017728>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/6885016>

⁵ <https://fairsharing.org/3773>

⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>

3.3 What is GA4GH Beacon?

Beacon⁷, developed through the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) Discovery workstream⁸, and with substantial support from ELIXIR, serves as a data discovery protocol and specification defining an open standard for discovering genomic and phenoclinic data in biomedical research and clinical applications.

The original version (v1) was designed to support minimal responses (yes/no) to queries about the presence of a given variant in datasets hosted by Beacon providers. Building upon the foundation laid by the original Beacon protocol, the Version 2 (v2) achieved recognition as a GA4GH standard in Spring 2022. This latest version introduces several features to enhance data discovery capabilities at source. Among these changes, there are expanded query options, enabling the retrieval of biological or technical (meta)data through filters defined via CURIEs. This includes parameters like phenotypes, disease codes, sex⁹, or age, providing researchers with a nuanced approach to data inquiries.

Beacon v2 is organised in two main blocks: the Beacon Framework and the Beacon Model. The Framework is agnostic to the knowledge domain and includes the features related to Beacon instance description (metadata), query requests, query responses, filters, handovers, and so on. The Beacon Models describe the domain entities and the relationships between them.

This dual-system approach not only broadens the scope for diverse Models – using different domains like images, pathogens, or infectious diseases– but also reinforces the adaptability of the Framework. The overall function of these components is to provide the instructions to design a REST API (REpresentational State Transfer Application Programming Interface) that could be implemented as a stand-alone product or, preferably, extending existing data management solutions.

Consequently, the 'beaconised' data represents a significant enhancement in data discoverability with minimal risks. Authorised users can now make a broad range of queries, ranging from positional requests for genomic variations in specified datasets (v1) to clinical and biomedical queries (v2).

⁷ <https://docs.genomebeacons.org/>

⁸ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/beacon-api/>

⁹*Note from the ethics reviewers: There is a limited representation of gender identities, and the classification may not account for intersex individuals or cases where sex is not clearly defined. However, gender was not considered, in compliance with the principles of data minimisation, since it was not a potential confounding factor in the causal model.*

4. Methods

The Beacon team has contributed extensively to the development, testing, and approval of the GA4GH Beacon v2 specification prior to the BY-COVID project. During the BY-COVID project, Beacons specific to COVID-19 have been deployed, and assistance has been provided to other teams to develop their own Beacon approaches.

Through close collaboration with WP3 (COVID-19 Integration Platform) and WP4 (Connecting the COVID-19 Data Platform to Analysis Tools and Local Portals), all relevant information related to data discovery at the source has been incorporated into the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk)¹⁰, enabling access to and re-use of infectious disease-related data for prospective pandemics. Additionally, efforts are underway to link entries within the COVID-19 Data Portal to accessible Beacons, increasing data accessibility and interoperability.

This deliverable is putting together the state of the art for data discovery at source¹¹ for COVID-19 & SARS-CoV-2. The approaches, current status and next steps are described in this document.

5. Description of work accomplished

5.1 Beacons with Infectious Diseases data (COVID-19)

During and after the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak, several teams and organisations have deployed beacons centred on COVID-19 and/or SARS-CoV-2 genomic and linked clinical data. As the official approval of the GA4GH Beacon version 2 was in April 2022, most of these beacons use an evolution of GA4GH Beacon version 1 or a preliminary draft of GA4GH Beacon version 2. This heterogeneity tampers the interoperability objective of Beacon, but, on the positive side, these beacons are illustrative of the type of data that COVID-19 or SARS-CoV-2 beacons are expected to include. They paved the way for the design of an interoperable COVID-19 Beacon based on the official Beacon v2 specification, and for extensions that could be required for infectious diseases.

The Beacon team contributed extensively to the GA4GH Beacon v2 specification prior to joining the BY-COVID project. As part of the BY-COVID project, the Beacon team has deployed beacons related to COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 and has assisted other teams in developing their own Beacon approaches.

¹⁰ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/data-sources/human-biomolecular-data>

¹¹ (as described above)

5.1.1 CRG viralBeacon

The CRG Covid Viral Beacon¹² is a tool designed to identify SARS-CoV-2 variability at the genomic, amino acid and motif level, along with other metadata.

It has been developed as a branch of the GA4GH Beacon standard, serving as a specialised use case for testing and demonstrating new features within Beacon v2 (and implicitly of Beacon v1). The choice of SARS-CoV-2 as a use case presented an opportunity to work with a compact genome, while its significance and urgency propelled a focused exploration of the utility of these features. The tool is well-aligned with the features currently offered by Beacon v2, including diverse query capabilities, filtering options, additional schemas for core entities, and support for handover to other solutions or extended data sources.

The development process has been organised as an iterative project, initially focusing on rapidly determining requirements and usage patterns and gradually transitioning towards adopting an orthodox Beacon v2 API interface. For example, in the initial iteration, data is presented "as is," without any harmonisation or preprocessing applied.

Figure 3: Variant query view of the CRG Viral Beacon

5.1.2 EGA Beacon (HGI)

The EGA Beacon¹³, managed by the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG), includes data from the COVID-19 Host Genetics Initiative (HGI) study¹⁴, a collaborative effort aimed at

¹² <https://covid19beacon.crg.eu/>

¹³ <https://beacon.ega-archive.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.covid19hg.org/>

facilitating research into the genetic factors influencing COVID-19. The data comprises nine distinct datasets, each offering unique insights through three main types of data: host phenoclinical data, raw host genotypes in plink format (bed, bim, fam), and host physiological lab parameters such as lymphocyte count.

The nine datasets¹⁵ — BelCovid_2, BRACOVID, GEN-COVID, Hostage_1, Hostage_2, Hostage_3, Hostage_4, INMUNGEN_CoV2, and SPGRX — provide a detailed look into patients affected by COVID-19, collectively including 3,957 patients and 5,247,741 single nucleotide variants (SNVs). The datasets are rich in information, encompassing a unified custom format for phenoclinical data stored in rds (R Data Serialization) files. These datasets are organised in tables with 36 variables, including patient and genotype identification, demographic details, comorbidities, hospitalisation information (within 30 days after a COVID-19 diagnosis), and COVID-19 related symptoms at admission.

The EGA Beacon interface (*Figure 4*), built using these comprehensive datasets, currently functions in production mode, providing all essential functionalities needed for advanced genomic research. It offers valuable insights into the human genetic landscape as it pertains to COVID-19, facilitating a deeper understanding of the disease. The EGA Beacon API is accessible at <https://ega-beacon-demo.ega-archive.org/api>.

The screenshot shows the EGA Beacon interface with a search query: `diseases=COVID-19, geneId:ACE2`. The interface includes several filter sections:

- Demographics:** Female, Male, Age, Weight, Height.
- Intervention:** Hospitalization, Intensive Care Unit Stay, Intubation (procedure), Oxygen administration by nasal cannula.
- Disease:** COVID-19 (checked), Immunocompromised, Asthma, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Chronic Kidney Disease, Hypertension, Organ Transplantation, Congestive Heart Failure, Myocardial Infarction, Stroke, Deep Vein Thrombosis, Reinfarction During Hospitalization.
- Variant:** Mutations in: gene: ACE2 (checked), alternateBases: T, referenceBases: C, start: 110173330, end: 110173331, type: SNP.

At the bottom left, there is a button labeled "All filtering terms".

Figure 4: Example of a query using the EGA Beacon for COVID-19 data.

¹⁵ <https://ega-archive.org/studies/EGAS00001005304>

5.1.3 COVID-NL Beacon

The COVID-NL Beacon is hosted by Health-RI¹⁶ and was set up in collaboration with Lygature and VUmc. This Beacon contains host phenoclinical data, which was acquired in different University Medical Centers (UMCs) throughout the Netherlands using the ISARIC COVID-19 Case Report Form (CRF)¹⁷. There are two versions of this CRF and each UMC decided by themselves whether to use the RAPID¹⁸ or CORE¹⁹ version. The RAPID CRF includes fewer variables than the CORE form and collected data are focused on specific risks, treatments and variables identified as priorities.

A first mapping to OMOP CDM²⁰ was created for 128 fields contained in the semantic COVID-19 CRF data model (RAPID version)²¹. This includes basic variables such as sex⁹, but also variables that describe measurements (e.g. body weight or heart rate), conditions (e.g. comorbidities or complications), observations (e.g. pregnancy or human coronavirus) and procedure (e.g. (non)invasive ventilation or antibiotic therapy). Drug exposure was not included completely for various reasons amongst which complexity and discussions about Intellectual Property. As a proof-of-concept, two drug exposures (i.e. ciprofloxacin and dopamine) were mapped and are available for query. It is envisioned that more drug exposure might be added in the future.

After the mapping to OMOP, a B4OMOP was deployed on the OMOP database (see [section 5.3.3](#)), which contains phenoclinical data based on a total of 1,563 patients from four different UMCs. Currently, COVID-NL Beacon is a proof-of-concept, so there is no graphic user interface and all mapped fields are visible on individual level (*Figure 5*). Using the overview of queryable fields²², filters can be applied as described on the B4OMOP GitLab²³.

¹⁶ <https://www.health-ri.nl/en>

¹⁷ <https://isaric.org/research/covid-19-clinical-research-resources/covid-19-crf/>

¹⁸ https://isaricdev.wpenginepowered.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/ISARIC-WHO-COVID-19-RAPID-CRF_EN.pdf

¹⁹ https://isaricdev.wpenginepowered.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/ISARIC-WHO-COVID-19-CORE-CRF_EN.pdf

²⁰ COVID-NL_ISARIC-OMOP_mapping.xlsx

²¹ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/COVIDCRFRAPID>

²² COVID-NL_filter_query_fields.xlsx

²³ https://gitlab.bsc.es/impact-data/impd-beacon_omopcdm/-/tree/main#example-get-queries

```

1 {
2   "meta": {
3     "beaconId": "bsc.omop.impact.beacon-test",
4     "apiVersion": "v2.0.0",
5     "returnedGranularity": "record",
6     "receivedRequestSummary": {
7       "apiVersion": "v2.0.0",
8       "requestedSchemas": [],
9       "filters": [],
10      "requestParameters": {},
11      "includeResultsetResponses": "HIT",
12      "pagination": {
13        "skip": 0,
14        "limit": 10
15      }
16    },
17    "requestedGranularity": "record",
18    "testNode": false
19  },
20  "returnedSchemas": [
21    {
22      "entityType": "individual",
23      "schema": "beacon-individual-v2.0.0"
24    }
25  ],
26  "responseSummary": {
27    "exists": true,
28    "numTotalResults": 1563
29  },
30  "response": {
31    "resultSets": [
32      {
33        "id": "",
34        "setType": "",
35        "exists": true,
36        "resultsCount": 1563,
37        "results": [
38          {
39            "id": "1",
40            "sex": {
41              "id": "Gender:M",
42              "label": "MALE"
43            },
44            "ethnicity": {
45              "id": "Race:3.01",
46              "label": "Black"
47            },
48            "diseases": [
49              {
50                "diseaseCode": {
51                  "id": "SNOMED:709044004",
52                  "label": "Chronic kidney disease"
53                },
54                "ageOfOnset": {
55                  "iso8601duration": "P17.0Y"
56                }
57              }
58            ]
59          }
60        ]
61      }
62    ]
63  }
64 }

```

```

1 {
2   "meta": {
3     "beaconId": "bsc.omop.impact.beacon-test",
4     "apiVersion": "v2.0.0",
5     "returnedGranularity": "record",
6     "receivedRequestSummary": {
7       "apiVersion": "v2.0.0",
8       "requestedSchemas": [],
9       "filters": [
10        {
11          "Gender": "F",
12          "SNOMED:427314002"
13        }
14      ],
15      "requestParameters": {
16        "filter": "OMOP Extension:OMOP5181835"
17      },
18      "includeResultsetResponses": "HIT",
19      "pagination": {
20        "skip": 0,
21        "limit": 10
22      }
23    },
24    "requestedGranularity": "record",
25    "testNode": false
26  },
27  "returnedSchemas": [
28    {
29      "entityType": "individual",
30      "schema": "beacon-individual-v2.0.0"
31    }
32  ],
33  "responseSummary": {
34    "exists": true,
35    "numTotalResults": 2
36  },
37  "response": {
38    "resultSets": [
39      {
40        "id": "",
41        "setType": "",
42        "exists": true,
43        "resultsCount": 2,
44        "results": [
45          {
46            "id": "1422",
47            "sex": {
48              "id": "Gender:F",
49              "label": "FEMALE"
50            },
51            "ethnicity": {
52              "id": "None:No matching concept",
53              "label": "No matching concept"
54            },
55            "diseases": [
56              {
57                "diseaseCode": {
58                  "id": "SNOMED:128238001",
59                  "label": "Chronic heart disease"
60                }
61              }
62            ]
63          }
64        ]
65      }
66    ]
67  }
68 }

```

Figure 5: Screenshot of the COVID-NL Beacon showing all 1,563 results without filters (left) and an example query that returned 2 females who are current smokers that received antiviral therapy (right)

5.1.4 University of Nottingham Beacon

The University of Nottingham Beacon is provided by the Centre for Health Informatics and Digital Research Service. Along with the mandatory Beacon endpoints, the *individuals* query endpoint has been implemented. The API is accessible at <https://beacon.nottingham.ac.uk/api> and the user interface (*Figure 6*) is available at <https://beacon.nottingham.ac.uk>. Filters defining phenoclinical concepts can be queried. The boolean “yes” or “no” response indicates if individuals are present that are associated with the queried filters.

Beacon is used as an entry point into the TRE-FX platform. TRE-FX enables federated analysis and learning across Trusted Research Environments (TREs). It uses data and computational infrastructure standards from GA4GH and ELIXIR to enable the execution of trusted workflows within TREs²⁴. Additionally, the “Five Safes RO-Crate”²⁵ is used which defines a standard Digital Object that represents a unit of computational workflow-based access to sensitive information managed in accordance with a set of principles conforming to the Five Safes framework²⁶. The use of a Five Safes RO-Crate to capture and output

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10529669>

²⁵ <https://trefx.uk/5s-crate/>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376350>

provenance information helps to ensure that analyses are reproducible. The Nottingham Beacon is an open demonstrator of the TRE-FX platform's discovery capabilities using the Beacon v2 API. Since this is a public interface, with no authentication and authorization restrictions, the backend OMOP database is populated with synthetic EHR data for COVID-19 patients (generated by Synthea²⁷). Although in this demonstrator the phenoclinical data are stored in the OMOP CDM²⁸, the TRE-FX platform is agnostic to the underlying data model. Future work will see the Beacon API enabled in TRE implementations using the TRE-FX platform, with more granular Beacon responses, e.g., counts with appropriate minimum-count thresholds.

University of Nottingham
UK | CHINA | MALAYSIA

Beacon

About

This Beacon uses the GA4GH Beacon v2 API specification and is provided by the Centre for Health Informatics and Digital Research Service at the University of Nottingham.
Beacon filters can be used to query a backend OMOP database of synthetic COVID-19 patient EHRs (electronic health records).
The Beacon will return **true** or **false** to indicate if the filters have been observed in any individuals.

Query

Select filtering terms

✓ There are individuals matching your query.

Selected

- SNOMED:271825005 - Respiratory distress
- SNOMED:386661006 - Fever
- Gender:F - FEMALE

Figure 6: University of Nottingham Beacon interface.

A backend OMOP database can be searched using Beacon filters (the logical AND operator is used between filters, as per the current Beacon specification).

5.1.5 BQC19 Bento

The Bento platform²⁹ has been developed by the C3G Data Team at the Canadian Centre for Computational Genomics, McGill University, Montréal, Canada, as a way to facilitate the discovery of the content for the BQC19 biobank datasets. The BQC19 biobank team is a multi-institutional group of researchers forming a decentralised infrastructure making it possible to federate the research efforts of all Quebec research institutions and facilitate national and international research collaborations.

²⁷ <https://synthea.mitre.org/downloads>

²⁸ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

²⁹ <https://bqc19.bento.sd4h.ca/#/en/>

The *Biobanque québécoise de la COVID-19* (BQC19) is a pan-provincial initiative that collects, stores and shares data and blood samples from COVID-19 patients, both severe and non-severe cases and control cases, in an effort to respond effectively to the public health challenges posed by the pandemic.

Participants (hosts) phenoclinical data over 1,000 properties, whole genome sequencing, genotyping, proteomics proteomics profiling (Olink and Somalogics), transcriptomics (RNA-Seq), viral genomes, metabolites profiling (ROCHE), antibody measurement, neutralising antibody titers. The phenoclinical data is ingested in, and extractable from the Bento platform using the GA4GH Phenopackets data exchange schema.

The platform is in production, and queryable using the user interface, and with the Beacon v2 API. The BQC19 cohort includes over 6,000 participants, from which more than 18,000 biological samples have been collected. Those samples have been digitised over multiple aspects with over 10,000 laboratory experiments including sequencing, proteomics and metabolites profiling, viral sequencing, and more.

Figure 7: McGill University Bento platform interface. Source: <https://bqc19.bento.sd4h.ca/#/en/>

5.1.6 SARS-CoV-2 whole genome sequencing circuit of Andalusia (Spain)

The SARS-CoV-2 whole genome sequencing circuit of Andalusia is a consortium that includes the main tertiary hospitals in the Andalusian region in Spain, the Computational Medicine Platform (<https://www.clinbioinfospa.es/>) – one of the research platforms of the Fundación Progreso y Salud (FPS) – the Technical Office for Information Management and the Regional Management of Public Health for the systematic sequencing of SARS-CoV-2 genomes for the contribution of epidemiological surveillance.

The circuit has been operating at full capacity since January 2021 and to date almost 40,300 complete SARS-CoV-2 genomes have been sequenced³⁰. A local *Nextstrain* instance is available with the phylogeny of a selection of sequenced viruses (<http://nextstrain.clinbioinfospa.es/SARS-COV-2-latest>). All viral genomes are sent to GISAID and ENA (PRJEB44396³¹, PRJEB47798³², PRJEB43166³³) databases and to the Andalusian Health Population Database (BPS, a resource with 13 million entries) where they are permanently stored and linked to the clinical information of patients.

The clinical information from a set of 320 patients with available SARS-CoV-2 genome have been mapped from the BPS database to OMOP. Some variables included are related to year of birth, gender, conditions, and drug exposure among others.

FPS is implementing a proof of concept, in which a clinical beacon on top of OMOP and a genomic beacon over the set of SARS-CoV-2 variants for the aforementioned dataset will be deployed for the query of viral and clinical information.

5.1.7 PathsBeacon

The Pathogen Surveillance Beacon, known as PathsBeacon³⁴, is hosted by Genomik Solidaritas Indonesia (GSI Lab), a prominent organisation in the genomics and healthcare sector in Indonesia. GSI Lab has been instrumental in supporting the COVID-19 response and is actively engaged in pathogen monitoring, rare disease research, and reproductive genomics.

The PathsBeacon project was initiated to monitor the progression of COVID-19 and other epidemiologically significant diseases. Over time, the project has expanded its focus to include the monitoring of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, particularly in the context of antibiotic resistance. PathsBeacon encompasses various types of data, including privately

³⁰ https://www.clinbioinfospa.es/COVID_circuit/

³¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB44396>

³² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB47798>

³³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB43166>

³⁴ <https://github.com/aehrc/COVID-sBeacon>

captured SARs-CoV-2 genomes and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* genomes sourced from public datasets. In addition to genomic data, PathsBeacon uses a custom metadata schema to store related patient attributes such as disease classification, symptomatic level, and fatal outcomes. This schema, presented in a tabular format, is visualised through a web-based user interface that features barplots and geoplots.

For the phenoclinical data, PathsBeacon employs a custom metadata schema built on top of Beacon version 1, specifically tailored for pathogen data. This schema includes information on location (country and state), patient status (symptoms categorised as mild, severe, or fatal), and collection dates. The system aggregates data upon query to display time series changes on the user interface. Currently, PathsBeacon³⁵ (Figure 8) operates in a developmental capacity on GSI Lab's AWS cloud infrastructure within the Indonesian region to ensure compliance. Access to PathsBeacon is restricted to authorised personnel for internal monitoring purposes.

PathsBeacon currently holds data for approximately 10,000 patients. The active user base comprises a group of 5-10 individuals who have direct access to the PathsBeacon deployment in their organisational AWS account.

Dataset name	Dataset Last Updated	Variant Count	Call Count	Samples	Total Samples	Frequency
Indonesia's SARS-CoV-2 data from GISAID	2021-09-14 09:02:36+10:00	1	6141	6141	6239	98.43 %

Position	Ref	Alt	Sift	Samples	Frequency
23403	A	G	0.30	6141	98.43

Figure 8: PathSBeacon interface

5.1.8 DNASTack Viral AI

Viral AI³⁶, developed by DNASTack, is a federated network for genomic variant surveillance and infectious disease research as collections of data related to COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2 and accessory data. It operates on a federated architecture, allowing the connection, analysis, and sharing of data without centralised control. Viral AI supports regional genomic surveillance initiatives and employs open standards from the GA4GH.

³⁵ <https://d2eqg84un4ipac.cloudfront.net/>

³⁶ <https://viral.ai>

Viral AI is supporting the Canadian COVID-19 Genomics Network (CanCOGeN) VirusSeq initiative³⁷, part of the national genomics program led by Genome Canada. Currently sharing sequencing data of over 150,000 viral samples from people testing positive for COVID-19 with more coordination of viral sequencing and associated clinical/epidemiological data collection between provinces and internationally.

The screenshot shows the 'VirusSeq SARS-CoV-2 Genome Sequences' page in the Viral AI interface. The page has a dark header with 'VIRAL AI' and a search bar. Below the header, there are tabs for 'Overview', 'Files', 'Samples', and 'Variants'. The main content area contains a detailed description of the CanCOGeN project, including its mission, data source, and access information. At the bottom, there are three data tables: 'Samples' with 563K rows, 'Variants' with 34M rows, and 'Files' with 2M rows. Each table has a search bar and a refresh icon.

Figure 9: Screenshot of Viral AI interface

5.1.9 Summary of example beacons

The following table provides a summary of the example beacons discussed in the sections above, highlighting the different types of data each beacon includes. This overview showcases the variety of data types managed by each beacon, illustrating their specific focuses and capabilities in the context of COVID-19 and other infectious diseases.

Table 1: Summary table of example beacons mentioned in the sections above³⁸

Beacon	Viral genomes	Patient basic data	Patient rich data	Patient genomics	Epidemiological data
viralBeacon	X	X	–	–	–
EGA (HGI)	–	X	X	X	–
COVID-19 NL	–	X	X	–	–

³⁷ <https://viral.ai/collections/virusseq/overview>

³⁸ The beacons described in the deliverable are examples of Beacon and beacon-like solutions related to COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2. Some were developed within the context of BY-COVID, while others were not. These beacons have been designed according to their specific source data.

U.Nottingham	–	X	X	–	–
BQC19	X	X	X	X	–
Andalusia	X	X	X	–	–
PathsBeacon	X	X	–	–	X
Viral AI	X	–	–	–	–

The table distinguishes several categories of data:

- Viral genomes: refer to raw or consensus sequences that could be directly queried.
- Patient basic data: refers to including just a few host properties like “sex”, “diagnose”
- Patient rich data: refers to having information like a case report with interventions or longitudinal aspects
- Patient genomics: applies when the beacon includes genomic data from the human donor
- Epidemiological data is information about strains, places where the virus has been spotted, strain frequency evolution, etc.

5.1.10 Infectious disease models

The example beacons above share different COVID-19 related data: some focused on the evolution of cases, hospitalisation and deaths, others in vaccination, strain evolution across the geography, etc. to cite some. This heterogeneity in contents demonstrates that infectious diseases domain is diverse and some community accepted models would be required for aspects like epidemiology or pathogen description.

The highlighted beacons implement different data models for clinical data, according to what was available at the time of the pandemic arrival, from ISARIC eCRF³⁹ (in different forms) to OMOP⁴⁰ or Phenopackets⁴¹. Although these models were appropriate and useful, they ended up suffering due to the lack of data availability, caused by the extreme workload of health organisations during the pandemic, that made proper data collection almost impossible. Additionally, given the need to organise data collection and to quickly analyse it, little attention was paid to harmonisation with other data collectors. For example, simple elements like the severity of the disease have different categories in different datasets. See ELIXIR CONVERGE Deliverable 7.2⁴² for a deeper description of this scenario. Additionally, these models were designed for COVID-19 or SARS-CoV-2, and are shallowly considering any other kind of infectious disease.

³⁹ <https://isaric.net/ccp/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

⁴¹ <https://phenopacket-schema.readthedocs.a/en/v2/index.html>

⁴² <https://zenodo.org/records/4893222>

5.2 A COVID-19 model for Beacon

5.2.1 The Beacon v2 Model general

GA4GH Beacon v2 includes a model for the clinical genomic diagnose domain (see *Figure 10*). This model is designed for a broad scope of diseases by focusing on attributes of individuals, their relatives, diseases, treatments, etc. The model fosters the use of ontologies to increase the interoperability of the hosted data.

Figure 10: A simplified view of the Beacon v2 Model

In comparison to the list of beacons in section [5.1.9](#), the Beacon v2 Model does not include information about the SARS-CoV-2 genomes (as in BQC19 Bento, Viral AI, and PathSBeacon) nor of the epidemiological data (as in PathSBeacon).

The Beacon model is largely based on Phenopackets (see [section below](#)), therefore, the discussion about it could be found in that section.

GA4GH Beacon was designed to help in the harmonisation at origin process and mapping from each beacon internal database model and schema to the Beacon v2 Model is the first step in such a process. This approach is useful in two different scenarios:

1. When the internal data model is proprietary and used solely in that project or institution.
2. When the institution or project has adopted a popular model like OHDSI OMOP CDM, HL7 FHIR⁴³ or GA4GH Phenopackets

In the first case, the institution team is the only one that could do a properly informed mapping between their model and the Beacon v2 Model. But, in the second case (*Figure*

⁴³ <https://hl7.org/fhir/>

11), any knowledgeable team could do a mapping and share it with the community. An example of this approach is [B4OMOP](#), developed by the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC) in the context of the Spanish IMPACT-Data project⁴⁴.

Figure 11: How Beacon v2 Model helps in further harmonising popular data models at origin

5.2.2 Phenopackets

Phenopackets⁴⁵ is a GA4GH standard for sharing disease and phenotype information to improve the ability to understand, diagnose, and treat both rare and common diseases. This standard consists of a schema that links detailed phenotypic descriptions with disease, patient, and genetic information, enabling clinicians, biologists, and disease and drug researchers to build more complete models of disease.

In July 2022, The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has published Phenopackets, becoming the first GA4GH standard published by ISO⁴⁶. This ISO standard provides a clear computational format for sharing individual patient traits, addressing a crucial need in disease diagnosis, treatment, and mechanism discovery.

As explained in a published article⁴⁷, Phenopackets Schema facilitates interoperability among databases, registries, and biobanks, supporting all types of diseases, including infectious diseases, diagnostics and case report representations. Furthermore, it aligns with other standards like VCF and FHIR, aiming to streamline genomic data analysis in clinical

⁴⁴ <https://impact-data.bsc.es/en/about/impact/>

⁴⁵ <https://phenopacket-schema.readthedocs.io/en/v2/index.html>

⁴⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79991.html>

⁴⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41587-022-01357-4>

settings. The schema's adoption is crucial for advancing precision medicine and leveraging genomic insights for disease understanding and therapy development.

The Phenopacket documentation (last accessed February 23th, 2024) includes an example of a real case⁴⁸ formatted as a phenopacket.

5.2.3 Is there a need for a new infectious diseases model?

The COVID-19 pandemic and the global efforts to collect and share data have demonstrated that this is a critical task but also a complex one. It has uncovered the need for better preparedness in the face of future pandemics and, hence, the need of a fast and effective global surveillance.

Infectious diseases are heterogeneous in aetiology, course and treatment. They are different among pathogens, e.g. tuberculosis is very different from ebola, and some diseases, like COVID-19, could have extremely different consequences in the infected people, from unnoticed to death or long covid. This adds another level of complexity in modelling such diseases.

As infectious diseases are heterogeneous, a model that aims to cover all or most of them would end up gravitating to a generalistic model, closer to existing models like OHDSI OMOP or HL7 FHIR. These models are designed to harmonise data coming from real-world healthcare, hence focusing on concepts like individual visits, tests, diagnoses, prescriptions or interventions. This approach speeds up the conversion from electronic health records to the model. However, they are too fine grain for the summarised vision that is required when doing higher view analysis. For example, when applied to cancer, the models lack the concept of lines of treatment, progression free, survival, neoadjuvant treatment, etc. Similarly, for COVID-19 they could miss concepts like overall severity, or long-covid diagnosis. These concepts could be inferred from single events like vaccination date, entering in the emergency room, moving to intensive care, etc. but the rules for inferring them could be quite complex, requiring manual curation and a significant amount of computing resources.

In consequence, a model for infectious diseases or several models tailored to different categories or aspects of infectious diseases, including epidemiology are needed. The models should preferably be accompanied by rules on how to infer specific values, e.g a consensus way on how to define “long covid” or disease severity.

Further efforts could be required, after BY-COVID, to integrate the different initiatives running in parallel to BY-COVID. These efforts could draw the then current landscape of models, interoperability and gaps among them.

⁴⁸ <https://phenopacket-schema.readthedocs.io/en/latest/covid19-example.html>

5.3 How to deploy a Beacon?

In order to deploy – or light – a Beacon v2, it is mandatory the integration of two fundamental elements.

- **Internal Database:** Serving as the repository for biological data, the internal database forms the cornerstone of the Beacon v2 implementation process. It acts as the reservoir from which genomic and phenoclinic data are sourced, enabling the Beacon to function effectively in its role of data discovery within biomedical research and clinical applications.
- **REST API:** Complementing the internal database, the REST API functions as the conduit through which standardised queries are transmitted and responses are received. These responses, varying from binary (yes/no) outcomes, counts, to comprehensive datasets, encapsulate the essence of Beacon v2's capacity to facilitate efficient data discovery.

This section describes different implementation options, each representing a spectrum of involvement or delegation in the context of Beacon v2.

5.3.1 On top of existing tools > API

The first option (*Figure 12*) is targeted to those organisations equipped with well-organised and structured data housed in databases, whether SQL or NoSQL, and possess the necessary resources and expertise to interpret and implement the Beacon v2 specification and construct an API on top of an existing tool.

Figure 12: Visual schema on how to implement a Beacon v2 API

Source: <https://docs.genomebeacons.org/implementations-options/>

5.3.2 As new deployment > B2RI

Recognising the inherent challenges involved in directly implementing a Beacon v2 API, particularly for centres without specialised personnel, CRG, within the framework of ELIXIR Beacon, has taken the lead in the development of the Beacon v2 Reference Implementation (B2RI) software⁴⁹. B2RI is an open-source set of tools designed for Linux, providing a practical solution for initiating a Beacon. B2RI includes tools for loading metadata, including phenotypic data, and genomic variants from a VCF file into a MongoDB database. It also features the Beacon query engine (REST API) and comes bundled with an example dataset (CINECA synthetic cohort EUROPE UK1⁵⁰) comprising synthetic data.

Developed as a customisable local solution, B2RI is delivered with a basic configuration. The software is written in Python, Perl, and Bash, offering a command-line interface (CLI) for control and operation. This design ensures accessibility and adaptability, allowing users to tailor B2RI to their specific requirements without unnecessary complexity or overselling. This software aids in the process of adapting data to meet Beacon v2 standards, referred to as "beaconisation." B2RI is designed to address the intricacies inherent in the Beacon v2 specification, aiming to simplify the implementation journey. It serves as a resource for centres seeking a pragmatic and user-friendly approach to seamlessly integrate Beacon v2 into their existing data infrastructure.

Figure 13: Visual schema on how to use Beacon v2 Reference Implementation to deploy a Beacon v2 API. Source: <https://docs.genomebeacons.org/implementations-options/>

5.3.2.1 How to load data into B2RI (Data Ingestion)

In the context of Beacon v2 implementation, B2RI simplifies data ingestion into three pivotal steps, ensuring seamless transformation and loading into MongoDB while adhering to Beacon v2 standards.

⁴⁹ <https://b2ri-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/synthetic-data/scd-europe-uk1>

B2RI streamlines the transformation of diverse data types, aligning them with Beacon v2 Models' prescribed format. The models, defined using JSON Schema, set the default schema for biological data responses. Then, a specialised tool within B2RI processes genomic data, utilising BCFtools, SnpEff, and SnpSift for annotation. As a result, a JSON file is generated with VCF data transformed into genomicVariations within Beacon v2 Models.

Finally, this transformed data, known as Beacon Friendly Format (BFF), can be easily loaded into a MongoDB, chosen for its compatibility, directly stores JSON files, eliminating the need for additional remapping. Within MongoDB, BFF files become collections, marking the conclusion of the data ingestion process.

Figure 14: schema on how to load data using Beacon v2 Reference Implementation.

Source: <https://github.com/EGA-archive/beacon2-ri-tools-v2?tab=readme-ov-file>

Additionally, there is the possibility to use BFF Genomic Variations Browser⁵¹ (Figure 15), a user-friendly visualisation tool that displays a subset of variants using HTML-tabs derived from gene lists.

⁵¹<https://b2ri-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/data-ingestion/#bff-genomic-variations-browser>

Job ID: 164054477710439 ► genomicVariationsVcf

Invitae_Multi_Cancer JSON | Cardiopathy JSON | Exome JSON

Displaying variants with Annotation Impact values equal to HIGH

Invitae_Multi_Cancer panel - 84 genes | Cardiopathy panel - 147 genes | Exome panel - 19206 genes

Show 10 variants

refseqId	position	referenceBases	alternateBases	variantType	genesId	molecularEffects	conditionId	clinicalRelevance
22	17072410	G	T	SNP	CCT8L2	missense_variant	not_provided(MedGen:CN517202)	benign
22	17565855	C	G	SNP	IL17RA,IL17RA	5_prime_UTR_variant, upstream_gene_variant	Immunodeficiency_51(MONDO:MONDO:0013500,MedGen:C4310803,OMIM:613953)	benign
22	17565887	C	A	SNP	IL17RA,IL17RA	5_prime_UTR_variant, upstream_gene_variant	Familial_Candidiasis_Recessive(MedGen:CN239217)	benign
22	17565931	T	C	SNP	IL17RA,IL17RA	5_prime_UTR_variant, 5_prime_UTR_variant	Familial_Candidiasis_Recessive(MedGen:CN239217)	benign
22	17565948	C	G	SNP	IL17RA,IL17RA	5_prime_UTR_variant, 5_prime_UTR_variant	Immunodeficiency_51(MONDO:MONDO:0013500,MedGen:C4310803,OMIM:613953)	benign

Figure 15: Screenshot of a local JSON file as a searchable table using BFF Genomic Variations Browser.

Source:

<https://b2ri-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/data-ingestion/#bff-genomic-variations-browser>

5.3.3 B4OMOP

The B4OMOP⁵² (Beacon for OMOP) is a development derived from the B2RI software, allowing the integration of a Beacon onto any OMOP CDM database, led by BSC with the guidance and support of CRG. The Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) is a standardised database structure for organising and analysing healthcare data from different sources. This commonly used database is designed to facilitate large-scale observational research and aims to enable researchers to generate reliable evidence for healthcare decision-making. OMOP CDM organises data into standardised tables with predefined formats, making it easier to harmonise data from disparate sources and conduct analyses across diverse healthcare datasets.

The deployment procedure works the same way as the B2RI, where initiating the container or performing a manual installation instantly configures a Beacon. However, now the application has a different backend infrastructure, where now the beacon queries a relational database based on the OMOP CDM.

Expert mapping between the OMOP CDM and Beacon models ensure alignment of elements such as diagnoses, treatments, laboratory results, exposures and biosample data.

⁵² https://gitlab.bsc.es/impact-data/impd-beacon_omopcdm

By using OMOP CDM as a base of querying data eliminates the need to convert data into Beacon Friendly Format (BFF), given the data already adheres to a recognised model. Therefore, institutions equipped with an OMOP CDM can deploy a Beacon within minutes.

5.3.4 B4TRE

The B4TRE is another development led by BSC and derived from the B2RI software that transmits messages to a Beacon inside of Trusted Research Environments (TREs). A Trusted Research Environment is a secure and controlled environment designed to facilitate sensitive research, particularly in fields of life sciences where privacy and data security are paramount.

Figure 16: In this schema a query is converted into a RabbitMQ message via B4TRE's User Interface (UI). The message enters the Demilitarised Zone (DMZ), an area between the public and the private space, before being transmitted to the secure zone via RabbitMQ. Within the secure zone, the message functions as a Beacon query. Subsequently, the beacon's response is relayed back to the user as a conventional UI response, again using RabbitMQ messaging.

Introducing an additional layer of security when accessing data through Beacon enhances data privacy. By preventing direct access to the Beacon, and subsequent database, within the TRE and enabling the TRE to monitor and log queries, privacy is safeguarded. Through the RabbitMQ messaging system, a POST Query is dispatched to the Beacon inside the TRE, with the response returning to the user via message, as it is explained in Figure 16.

6. Results

The WP2 partners in the BY-COVID project have achieved significant milestones in advancing the GA4GH Beacon specification and implementing the Reference Implementation v2, chronologically starting with the CRG viralBeacon ([5.1.1](#)) initiative.

Through collaborative efforts with the GA4GH community, the project contributed to expanding query options within the Beacon v2 specification. This includes enabling the retrieval of biological and technical metadata using filters defined via CURIEs, allowing for more nuanced data inquiries. Furthermore, BY-COVID played a pivotal role in broadening the scope of Beacon Models, facilitating adaptability across diverse domains such as infectious diseases. This flexibility enhances the interoperability of Beacons and supports the inclusion of additional data sources beyond genomic variations.

Leveraging advancements in the Beacon specification, the project successfully deployed instances of viralBeacon focused on COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 data. These instances serve as examples of Beacon v2 implementation, demonstrating the practical application of enhanced query capabilities and model flexibility.

In addition to deploying its own Beacons, the project provided guidance and support to other teams in developing their Beacon approaches. This collaborative effort fostered knowledge sharing and contributed to the broader adoption of Beacon standards within the research community.

These accomplishments stem from collaborative efforts involving various project partners and are supported in part by funding from BY-COVID project.

7. Next steps

From the work in WP2, several potential next steps were envisioned:

- BY-COVID in ELIXIR Beacon Network: The ELIXIR Beacon Network (EBN) aims to act as a resource to facilitate data discoverability by enabling users to search across multiple Beacons simultaneously in a single query. Created under the framework of ELIXIR, this network establishes an interconnected ecosystem of beacons, fostering responsible sharing of genomic, phenotypic and other data types. In order to optimise the use of resources when running a service, BY-COVID related beacons could be integrated in the EBN and discoverable by the regular Beacon search (e.g. “SARS-CoV-2” or “COVID-19” ontology terms).
- Contributing in the development of infectious diseases models: In particular, members of institutions participating in BY-COVID are actively participating in the 1+MG Infectious Diseases and European Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI) working groups and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health Infectious Disease

Community (partnership with PHA4GE). The eventual goal of such participation is to design a pathogen extension for the Beacon specification.

- Document all relevant information on how to deploy a beacon and the various products (e.g., B2RI, B4OMOP) into the RDMkit⁵³, creating a general knowledge base for data management. Additionally, include a list of beacons related to COVID-19 in the IDTk⁵⁴.
- Outline the landscape of data discoverability for open-access data in the next WP2 deliverable, D2.4, titled “Report on data sources discovery and integration for enabling data use and re-use in response to future outbreaks.”

8. Impact

Deliverable D2.3 showcases the significant progress and innovations achieved by WP2 partners within the BY-COVID project and beyond. The report not only delineates existing data discovery mechanisms but also introduces novel cross-domain data discovery methods through extensions to the Beacon v2 technologies, with a particular emphasis on COVID-19 data.

Throughout the project, substantial advancements have been made in expanding standard data discovery mechanisms. Collaborative efforts have enhanced Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) Beacon-based mechanisms, enabling efficient data discovery directly at the source. This deliverable documents eight distinct Beacon implementations by BY-COVID partners and other institutions across Europe, Canada, and Australia. These Beacons facilitate the sharing of cross-domain data, encompassing viral genomes, epidemiological data, rich patient information, and combined viral and host genomes from the same donors.

These achievements underscore a strong commitment to enabling data discovery at its source. By extending Beacon technologies, the project has significantly improved data accessibility and interoperability across various research domains, marking a pivotal step forward in facilitating data discovery, fostering collaboration, and enabling more effective use of data resources in the fight against COVID-19 and future pandemics.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

The initial goal was to address the discovery of all types of data, both open and controlled access. However, due to the delay of this deliverable and the project's imminent conclusion, it was decided to streamline efforts. As Deliverable D2.3 and Deliverable D2.4 are now due around the same time, the WP2 team collectively agreed to concentrate exclusively on

⁵³ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

controlled access data in this deliverable. The discussion of open data discovery will be covered separately in Deliverable D2.4.